

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

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D6.1: DEC Strategy

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Summary Sheet

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
2. CITY-MOVE's Objectives	7
CITY-MOVE Deliverables and Milestones	9
3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy	10
Communication	11
Dissemination	11
Exploitation	12
4. Target Groups	12
5. Key Project Messages	13
6. DEC Channels	13
6.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Channels	13
6.2 Communication Channels	14
7. Activities and Outputs	15
Communication	15
Dissemination	17
Exploitation	18
8. Outputs and DEC Indicators	19
9. Communications Tactics	20
Project Identity	20
10. Timeline	23
11. Annexes	24
Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network	24
Annex 2. Identified City-GAPPA Interventions	25
Lima	25
Bogotá	26
Kampala	26
Antwerp	26
Rotterdam	26
Ljubljana	27
Annex 3. Identified Relevant Scientific Journals	27

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
CCAB	Cross-City Advisory Board
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DECS	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy
CoPs	Communities of Practice
HCPs	Health Care Practitioners
GAPPA	Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030
GRIPP	Getting research into policy & practice
LLs	Living Labs
MCDA	Multiple Criteria Decision Assessment
NCDs	Noncommunicable Diseases
NGOs	Non-Governmental Entities
NMT	Non-Motorised Transport (walking and cycling)
PA	Physical Activity
PAR	Participatory Action Research
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UN	United Nations
W21	Walk21
WHO	World Health Organisation
WPs	Work Packages
WoS	Web of Science, indexed journals

Glossary

City-GAPPA. Selected interventions in each city. Adaptation of the GAPPA to the selected interventions at the city-level.

Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030 (GAPPA). The new WHO global action plan to promote physical activity responds to the requests by countries for updated guidance, and a framework of effective and feasible policy actions to increase physical activity at all levels. It also responds to requests for global leadership and stronger regional and national coordination, and the need for a whole-of-society response to achieve a paradigm shift in both supporting and valuing all people being regularly active, according to ability and across the life course ([WHO, 2018](#)).

Living Labs. Sites where multiple stakeholders from different domains (science, society, government, business) can work on complex urban challenges through co-production, experimentation, and learning.

Multiple Criteria Decision Assessment (MDCA). A tool that helps urban decision-makers and stakeholders with assessing the desirability of interventions in cities on selected criteria and the performance of the interventions on these criteria.

Noncommunicable Diseases (NCDs). Also known as chronic diseases, tend to be of long duration and are the result of a combination of genetic, physiological, environmental, and behavioural factors. The main types of NCD are cardiovascular diseases (such as heart attacks and stroke), cancers, chronic respiratory diseases (such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma) and diabetes ([WHO, 2023](#)).

Theory of Change. The CITY-MOVE ToC will be created using the accumulated project evidence to support the replication and scaling up of city interventions for NCD risk reduction. The CITY-MOVE ToC enables researchers and implementers to take a system's perspective to the evaluation of the city-GAPPA interventions in 6 cities.

Executive Summary

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (DECS) for the CITY-MOVE project aims to identify opportunities for outreach and engagement; plan appropriate activities; ensure complementarity of communication channels, tools and materials; and identify feedback loops of the outreach and communication process to the Work Packages (WP's). The strategy for Exploitation includes a wider engagement strategy beyond CITY-MOVE. For Communication and Dissemination, activities will include the development and deployment of information, tools, channels and platforms for the targeted stakeholders, and engagement in wider dissemination of the CITY-MOVE content. This includes the CITY-MOVE brand identity with key templates and a project website as the main promotional channel and promotion of events in Communities of Practice (CoP) regions, and an International Conference in Ljubljana on successful approaches for delivering city-Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030 (GAPPA).

1. Introduction

City environments are a key determinant of noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) through several intersecting social, cultural and environmental factors. Cities are associated with lower physical activity (PA), unhealthy diets, overweight and obesity. Environmental factors in cities also influence NCDs (cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory illnesses, diabetes, and cancers).

Transport systems, building and street designs, and land use patterns also impact NCDs through their influence on air quality, PA, blood pressure, and obesity. Cities are thus both a threat to health and a potential enabler of change. Given the untapped potential of cities to promote PA, CITY-MOVE focuses on adapting the GAPPa to the city-level (city-GAPPa).

CITY-MOVE aims to accelerate and support action for PA at the city level in six cities across three continents: Europe (Antwerp, Ljubljana, and Rotterdam), Africa (Kampala) and Latin America (Bogotá and Lima), to learn from interventions in different phases and in diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts.

2. CITY-MOVE's Objectives

CITY-MOVE's overall goal is to accelerate and support interventions for physical activity at the city level focusing on six cities that have shown the commitment and ownership to make progress.

Specific CITY-MOVE Objectives

1. Develop a comprehensive and comparative CITY-MOVE Theory of Change and operationalised measures for stakeholder engagement and context analysis.
2. Adapt and refine city-GAPPA to six cities across three continents, through engagement with local stakeholders addressing key uncertainties and resources in each context.
3. Support cities in the successful implementation of early phase city-GAPPA interventions through action research in Living Labs.
4. Assess acceptability, reach, adoption, feasibility, fidelity, adaptation and sustainability of selected city-GAPPA interventions in each city.
5. Improve the development and utilisation of routinely collected data as a tool to support successful implementation.
6. Generate cross-contextual evidence on implementation, evaluation and scalability through multi-criteria decision assessment for 13 interventions in 6 cities (see table below).
7. Generate global capacity on best implementation practices and transferability of city-GAPPA beyond the 6 cities.

Table 1. Identified city-GAPPA actions. (See Annex 2. Identified City-GAPPA Actions for detailed descriptions).

Region	City	Stage	PA Initiative	Target / Reach	GAPPA Objective
Latin America	Lima	Early	Pan American Games Legacy	(target: 20,000)	Active Environments
		Late	Green Belt Independencia	(reach: 210,000)	Active Societies
	Bogotá	Early	Happiness Centres	(target: 10,000)	Active Environments
		Late	CicloVía	(reach: 1,400,000)	Active Societies
Africa	Kampala	Early	Annual Car-Free Day	(target: 830,000)	Active Societies
		Late	NMT Pilot Corridor	(reach: 714,000)	Active Environments
Europe	Antwerp	Early	Safe Streets for Girls	(target: 5,500)	Active Societies
		Late	Health Kiosk	(reach: 3,600)	Active People
		Failed	Square Full of Health		Active Environments
	Rotterdam	Early	Green Connection	(unknown)	Active Environments
		Late	Green Walking Routes	(unknown)	Active People
	Ljubljana	Early	Walking Gaming App	(target: 7,000)	Active People
Late		Walk Along the Wire Event	(reach: 3,000)	Active Societies	

CITY-MOVE Deliverables and Milestones

The launch of the following deliverables and milestones are to be integrated into the DEC Strategy:

2024

- **M7.1.** Kick-off consortium meeting organised (Q2, 2024)
- **M6.1.** Skills and training audit performed (Q2, 2024)
- **M3.1.** TIDieR description of late interventions (Q2, 2024)

2025

- **D1.2. Legacy CITY-MOVE ToC.** Final report with legacy CITY-MOVE ToC (Q1, 2025)
- **M1.3.** Core context elements identified (Q1, 2025)
- **D1.1. CITY-MOVE ToC.** Report of the initial CITY-MOVE ToC (Q2, 2025)
- **M2.1.** First co-production session held in each city (Q2, 2025)
- **M5.1.** Defining the decision problem (Q2, 2025)
- **M6.2.** First meeting of each regional CoP (Q2, 2025)
- **M7.3.** CCAB established (Q2, 2025)
- **D5.1. MDCA core set.** A core process, cost (-effectiveness) and outcome indicator set for MCDA (Q4, 2025)

2026

- **M5.2.** Collecting performance data (Q1, 2026)
- **D3.1. Intervention evaluation.** Implementation evaluation report of late interventions (Q2, 2026)
- **M2.2.** LL session in each city on early phase implementation issues, local needs, tailoring (Q2, 2026)
- **D2.1. Co-Production.** Report on co-production sessions (Q4, 2026)
- **M4.1.** Guidance document on how cities can get maximal impact from routine data (Q4, 2026)
- **M5.3.** Assess desirability of interventions 5 36 Workshop reports (Q4, 2026)

2027

- **M4.2.** 6 city plans to strengthen monitoring and effect evaluation (Q2, 2027)
- **M5.4.** Sensitivity analysis outputs (Q2, 2027)
- **D3.2. Cross-settings lessons.** Report on cross-settings implementation and evaluation lessons & recommendations (Q3, 2027)
- **D5.2. Generic MCDA tool.** Generic MCDA tool applicable to evaluate the desirability of city-GAPPA interventions (Q4, 2027)
- **D6.2. Conference.** International conference in Ljubljana (Q4, 2027)

3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy

The three terms are defined by Horizon Europe guidelines as follows (European Commission, European Research Executive Agency):

- *Communication: Inform, promote, and communicate activities and results.*
- *Dissemination: Make knowledge and results publicly available.*
- *Exploitation: Make concrete use of results.*

CITY-MOVE distinguishes between three levels of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC): **1) local level** within the six cities: between city and public health authorities, stakeholders, implementing partners, researchers and communities; **2) regional level** of Europe, LA and East Africa; and **3) global level** including global organisations and the scientific community.

CITY-MOVE strategy builds on the strong networks of the CITY-MOVE consortium and includes capacity building activities. It will activate multiplier channels to amplify messages, enhancing the project's visibility and supporting the replication of actions and sustain their impacts well beyond the lifetime of the project. This includes boosting the visibility of dissemination in international partnerships and national agencies responsible for NCDs, through participation in key international, regional, and national fora, events and dialogue processes and relevant local, national, and regional events.

At local level, consortium members frequently collaborate with city authorities, NGOs, HCPs, public health institutes, and these personal networks will be leveraged for direct dissemination. Consortium members have connections to international organisations and networks that will be leveraged for dissemination ([Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network](#)).

Partners with connections to these networks will ensure that CITY-MOVE outputs are distributed through newsletters, webinars and events hosted by the networks.

Dissemination will also include cooperation with local media, featuring project actions and partners, research, and innovation channels, including open access journals and innovation highlights shared in relevant platforms and fora. All results will be disseminated as soon as possible acknowledging the EU funding.

Exploitation of results is done in 6 cities directly and through the regional Communities of Practice (CoPs) to extend the scale to other cities in EUR, LA and East Africa. Digital access to CITY-MOVE products, via the open access database/repository, the W21 [knowledge library](#) (a global research, policy and projects database) and '[Pathways map](#)' (A map-based platform that shows strategic insights into every country's state of walking) will facilitate exploitation.

Exploitation in LA and East Africa will indirectly also be in the European Union's interest, since improvement of the build and social environments in those cities will stimulate social and economic

development (Annex 3. Identified Relevant Scientific Journals) and will be available via open access to policymaking for the improvement of current PA policies and programmes in cities.

CITY-MOVE DECS overall objective is **to extend the scale of impact beyond the six cities and to sustain impacts beyond the lifetime of CITY-MOVE.**

CITY-MOVE DECS also has a set of **primary and secondary objectives** as follows:

Communication

Objective 1. Effectively showcase and amplify the activities and outcomes of the project at the international, regional and local levels.

Objective 1.1. International Level. At the international level, emphasise the project's global relevance and contributions to the wider field with support of the international stakeholders (Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network). **Outcome:** Develop a robust international communication framework that leverages partnerships with global stakeholders in the CITY-MOVE Network to amplify the project's contributions to the international community.

Objective 1.2. Regional Level. Regionally, the focus will be on the specific benefits and implications for regional stakeholders (Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network), aligning with the capacity building and Communities of Practice (CoP) that will be established in the C-M project time. **Outcome:** Enhance regional impact through tailored initiatives that address specific regional needs and build capacity, in alignment with the Communities of Practice developed throughout the project.

Objective 1.3. City Level. Locally, the focus will be on showcasing the impacts of the adaptation of the GAPPAs to the city level and the Living Labs, while promoting continuous dialogue & engagement of local stakeholders (based on the community asset maps T1.2), in capacity-building events and other CITY-MOVE activities that aim to accelerate and support PA interventions. **Outcome:** Achieve local transformation through targeted engagement and the implementation of Living Labs and other local initiatives that demonstrate the practical application of the GAPPAs at the city level.

Dissemination

Objective 2. Promote the data and findings from the evaluation of 13 PA interventions (Annex 2. Identified City-GAPPAs Actions) ensuring that these findings are accessible and understandable to a diverse range of stakeholders.

Objective 2.1. Publicise and raise awareness of the project's open access repositories, other databases and cross-contextual evidence on implementation considering the Data Management Plan, evaluation and scalability of each intervention while demonstrating its practical application, and potential use. **Outcome:** Establish a comprehensive awareness campaign that effectively highlights and promotes the use of the project's open access repositories, databases, and evidence.

Objective 2.2. Develop clear, engaging, and targeted messaging tailored to stakeholders to present each intervention (stage, outcomes, evaluation lessons and recommendations) and

highlight the broader implications of these findings. **Outcome:** Develop and implement a targeted communication strategy that effectively conveys the stages and implications of each intervention, tailored to different stakeholder needs.

Exploitation

Objective 3. Position CITY-MOVE as a notable contribution in the field of PA while raising awareness, showcasing the results of the project, and promoting the replication of the city-GAPPA interventions.

Objective 3.1. Present successful approaches for delivering city-GPPA at an International conference, thereby establishing a global platform for the dissemination of the findings and promoting replication and fostering academic and professional collaborations. **Outcome:** Successfully present city-GPPA strategies at an international conference, establishing a recognized platform that encourages global dissemination, replication, and collaboration.

Objective 3.2. Enhance the knowledge on digital access to CITY-MOVE products, via the open access database/repository. **Outcome:** Broaden the reach and usability of the CITY-MOVE products through enhanced digital access via the open access database/repository.

Objective 3.3. Promote the use of the CITY-MOVE MCDA tool for the development and improvement of PA policies. **Outcome:** Increase the adoption and utilization of the CITY-MOVE MCDA tool among policymakers and stakeholders for the development and improvement of PA policies.

4. Target Groups

Table 2. CITY-MOVE target groups.

Local Level within six cities	City Departments (planning, health, sport, transport)
	Public health institutes, prevention services
	NGOs
	Public health authorities
	Health care practitioners
	People living in cities
	People in specific target groups
Regional Latin America, East Africa, Europe	Above actors in other cities
Global	Scientific community
	Global and regional organisations

5. Key Project Messages

- Cities are a potential enabler of change to increase PA.
- CITY-MOVE offers a unique exploration and evaluation of 13 city-GAPPA interventions across diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts (6 cities and 3 continents).
- CITY-MOVE is a valuable knowledge hub for the successful implementation of adaptable PA interventions (based on the GAPPA).
- CITY-MOVE accelerates and supports action for PA.
- To be expanded in function of results

6. DEC Channels

6.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Channels

Table 3. Targets and channels for dissemination and exploitation

Level	Target Group	Relevant Results	Goal of Dissem.	Dissem. Channel	Potential Exploitation	Measurable results
Local within six cities	City Departments (planning, health, sport, transport)	Successful implementation of city-GAPPA interventions; LL method; MDCA for 13 interventions; core process & outcome set	Getting research into policy & practice (GRIPP)	Living labs; policy dialogues & brief; direct contact with policy makers; policy brief	Living lab method, intervention lessons learnt, MCDA taken up in new interventions	12 policy makers/city reached through LL/ dialogue; 50 policy makers / city receive brief
	Public health institutes, prevention services	Evidence on implementation of city-GAPPA and its effects	GRIPP	Living Labs; direct messages with leaders/managers	Integration of results in quality improvement	3 staff/city reached through LL; 20 staff
	NGOs	Stakeholder assessment & community mapping tools; implementation outcomes in 6 cities	Increase implementation capacity	Living Labs; direct messages with leaders; website & repository	Results taken up in scaling up and in new interventions	4 NGOs / city reached through LL; 10 NGOs/city receive messages; 500 access website
	Public health authorities	Evidence on implementation of city-GAPPA	GRIPP	Implementation guidelines	Integration in quality improvement	10 staff/ city receive guidelines

	Health care practitioners	Information on city-GAPPA benefits for target groups; guidelines	More PA promotion in health care	Living Labs; direct info to HCPs; training event	Guidelines used in PA counselling, referrals	2 HCPs/city reached in LL; 50/city receive info; 2 trainings/ city
	People living in cities	Information on interventions & benefits of PA	Increased awareness & knowledge	News media; podcasts; social media	NA	5 news articles/ city; 500 podcast listeners; 1000 followers/channel
	People in specific target groups	Adaptation of implementation to their needs	Increased awareness & knowledge	Targeted & social media; direct contact w/ representing orgs	Capacity for tailoring used in other interventions	5 articles targeted media; 1000 followers/channel; 5 orgs/city reached
Regional Latin America, East Africa, Europe	Above actors in other cities	Guidance on how to use MDCA in new contexts; knowledge & skills survey; capacity database	Increase regional capacity for implementation of city-GAPPA	CoP; online repository; direct messages to city networks; conference presentations	CoP sustained; above tools taken up in other cities	20 participants/ CoP meeting; 500 visits to repo./ year; 10 messages /year; 5000 attendees
Global	Scientific community	ToC, frameworks & methods developed; evidence on (implement) outcomes	Contribution to state of the art	Open access journals; Conference presentations	Uptake in new (research) projects	5000 paper downloads; 5000 conference attendees
	Global and regional organisations	Evidence city-GAPPA implementation; MCDA framework for contextualisation	Contribution to global targets	Participation in high-level meetings and via networks	Uptake in global action plans & best practices	5 invitations to global events; 10 citations in global reports

6.2 Communication Channels

Table 4. Communication measures

Level	Method/Channel	Target group	Description	Measurable results
Within the consortium	Face to face consortium meetings	Researchers & city partners	2 in-person events for reciprocal learning start/end	2 meetings 50 participants/meeting
	Online consortium meetings	Researchers	Monthly meetings for progress & reciprocal learning	48 meetings 18 participants/ meeting

Between the consortium and funder	EU-organisations and websites	Funders, EU policy-makers, member states	Project deliverables on CORDIS, other channels to discuss with EU	13 publications on EU websites; 10 interactions with EU stakeholders
Between the consortium and users	CITY-MOVE website	General public	Project & team info, outputs	5000 visitors/yr. to website
	Policy briefs	Decision-makers at the city and global levels	Introduction to MCDA framework and its use	1 policy briefs produced /city and disseminated (views)
	Blogs, podcasts, videos	Specific target groups of city-GAPPA	Benefits & details of city-GAPPA interventions	20 blogs, 20 podcasts, 12 videos; 500 views /listens (to be adapted to the project and contextual needs)
	Guidelines, trainings	Professionals & implement organisations	Education & instruction materials on WP outputs	50 participants, 100 users and 500 downloads

7. Activities and Outputs

Communication

Objective 1. Effectively showcase and amplify the activities and outcomes of the project at the international, regional, and local levels.

Objective 1.1. International Level. At the international level, emphasise the project's global relevance and contributions to the wider field with support of the international stakeholders ([Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network](#))

Strategy 1.1.A Digital Presence.

Activity 1.1.1. Project Branding. Create the visual identity and brand guidelines to ensure consistency across all communication platforms. **Output:** Branding Manual.

Activity 1.1.2. Website development. Create a CITY-MOVE website that will serve a repository of the project findings for anyone interested. **Output:** Project's Website

Activity 1.1.3. Social Media. Create the project's social media LinkedIn and X channels. **Output:** Social media handles.

Strategy 1.1.B. Creation of informative materials.

Activity 1.1.4. Social Media Campaigns. Develop clear messaging and social media campaigns focused on the DEC of [CITY-MOVE Deliverables and Milestones](#) and on the contributions of CITY-MOVE to the international agenda. **Output:** Yearly DEC programming.

Activity 1.1.5. Articles, blogs and podcasts. Write articles, blog posts and create/participate in podcasts that: i) position the project leaders as global experts in their field on a global scale, ii) showcase the contributions of the project to PA and how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges. **Output:** 5 news articles/4 Podcasts (to be adapted to the project and contextual needs).

Activity 1.1.6. Partner Newsletters and Events. Promote CITY-MOVE results in partner's newsletters, webinars and events hosted by the networks. **Output:** Project published in 1-2 global partner newsletters/events per year.

Strategy 1.1.C. Boost internal communications.

Activity 1.1.7. Project Meetings. Organise in-person reciprocal learning meetings for the start and end of the project, and monthly online consortium meetings. **Output:** Initial and final reciprocal learning meetings.

Activity 1.1.8. Online project meetings. Organise monthly meetings to discuss the progress and next steps of the project. **Output:** Monthly meetings with 18 participants per meeting.

Objective 1.2. Regional Level. Regionally, the focus will be on the specific benefits and implications for regional stakeholders ([Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network](#)), aligning with the capacity building and Communities of Practice (CoP).

Strategy 1.2. Showcase CITY-MOVE regional presence.

Activity 1.2.1. CoP platform for regional exchange. Use social media channels to promote the presence of CITY-MOVE, the activities, and participants of the CoPs. **Output:** Messaging and programming defined.

Activity 1.2.2. Partner's Newsletters. Use the existing newsletters of the project's consortium to showcase CITY-MOVE's progress and activities, including the CoPs and Living Labs (LL), every semester. **Output:** Project showcased in 2 regional partner newsletters per year.

Objective 1.3. City Level. Locally, the focus will be on showcasing the impacts of the adaptation of the GAPPA to the city level and the Living Labs, while promoting continuous dialogue & engagement of local stakeholders (based on the community asset maps T1.2), in capacity-building events and other CITY-MOVE activities that aim to accelerate and support PA interventions.

Strategy 1.3. Showcase city progress and participation.

Activity 1.3.1. Promote the City's progress and the Living Labs (LL). Use social media channels to promote the presence and progress of CITY-MOVE and the Living Labs. **Output:** Messaging and programming defined.

Activity 1.3.2. Local Media Network. Create a database of local media contacts to future project actions (See activity 2.2.3). **Output:** Local press/media database created.

Dissemination

Objective 2. Promote the data and findings from the evaluation of 13 PA interventions ([Annex 2. Identified City-GAPPA Actions](#)) ensuring that these findings are accessible and understandable to a diverse range of stakeholders.

Objective 2.1. Enhance Visibility. Publicise and raise awareness of the project's open access repositories, other databases and cross-contextual evidence on implementation, evaluation and scalability of each intervention while demonstrating its practical application, and potential use considering the Data Management Plan.

Strategy 2.1. Share evidence and findings of city-GAPPA.

Activity 2.1.1. Getting research into policy & practice (GRIPP). Create and distribute comprehensive policy briefs, guides on how to effectively use the MCDA tool for policy-making development and share evidence on implementation of city-GAPPA and its effects with city leaders/staff through the LL. **Output:** Policy briefs delivered.

Objective 2.2. Strategic Communication Development. Develop clear, engaging and targeted messaging to present each intervention (stage, outcomes, evaluation lessons and recommendations) and highlight the broader implications of these findings.

Strategy 2.2. Showcase the results of the projects.

Activity 2.2.1. Present the results of the Living Labs (LL). Use social media to showcase the challenges addressed in the LL and the results of the co-creation processes while highlighting the impact and importance of Action Research in CITY-MOVE. **Output:** LL's progress and results showcased in social media.

Activity 2.2.2. Social Media City Progress. Post clear messages to showcase CITY-MOVE's progress, city-GAPPA interventions, and results of cross-context evaluation & transferability. **Output:** City's progress and results showcased in social media.

Activity 2.2.3. Press releases. Prepare and distribute press releases to present the results of the project at the local level and the connection with other CITY-MOVE cities actions acknowledging the EU funding. **Output:** 5 articles published in targeted media.

Activity 2.2.4. Scientific publications. Present the project's results as peer-reviewed publications, in open-access scientific journals and conferences. **Output:** 4 cross-city articles published in high impact journals; 12 articles presented on city findings in WoS indexed journals and results presented at international conferences.

Activity 2.2.5. CORDIS. Publish the results of the project in CORDIS EU Results, a platform on projects, topics, and publications funded by the EU's research programs. **Output:** 13 publications on EU websites; 10 interactions with EU stakeholders.

Strategy 2.3. Training workshops.

Activity 2.3.1. Skills & training audit (T6.1). Diffuse city-GAPPA capacity audit across the 3 global regions, targeting key agencies, managers and key implementers working in city

departments, public health organisations and ministries and define the needs assessment of the key management challenges identified in city-GAPPA. **Output:** Training content available on website.

Activity 2.3.2. Peer-to-peer support & training of junior researchers. At the consortium level, facilitate interdisciplinary support and learning between researchers, policy makers and implementers through the Cross-City Advisory Board (CCAB). **Output:** Capacity building plan

Exploitation

Objective 3. Position CITY-MOVE as a notable contribution in the field of PA while raising awareness, showcasing the results of the project, and promoting the replication of the city-GAPPA interventions.

Objective 3.1. Global Dissemination and Collaboration. Present successful approaches for delivering city-GAPPA at an International conference, thereby establishing a global platform for the dissemination of the findings and promoting replication and fostering academic and professional collaborations.

Strategy 3.1. Showcase the project at an international level.

Activity 3.1.1. Knowledge sharing in Ljubljana Conference. Present the results of the projects and the successful approaches for delivering the city-Global Action Plan on Physical Activity at Walk21 Ljubljana. **Output:** Project's results presented in an international conference.

Global level: uptake through global events and organisations such as NCD Alliance (<https://ncdalliance.org/>) and healthy cities network (<https://www.who.int/europe/groups/who-european-healthy-cities-network>)

Activity 3.1.2. Share the Knowledge Library. Facilitate exploitation through inclusion of the project in W21's Knowledge Library and Pathways Map. **Output:** Inclusion of CITY-MOVE publications in the Knowledge Library.

Objective 3.2. Digital access promotion. Enhance the knowledge on digital access to CITY-MOVE products, via the open access database/repository.

Strategy 3.2. Showcase CITY-MOVE's open access repositories and databases.

Activity 3.2.1. Repository Promotion. Share the repository with stakeholders and launch a Did you know? communications campaign based on the key findings/data found in CITY-MOVE's repository (T6.3). **Output:** Messaging and programming defined.

Objective 3.3. MCDA tool promotion. Promote the use of the CITY-MOVE MCDA tool for the development and improvement of PA policies.

Strategy 3.3. Engage with policymakers to demonstrate how the database can inform public policy or decision-making processes.

Activity 3.3.1. MDCA tool promotion. Create and implement a communication campaign to promote the results and use of CITY-MOVE's MDCA tool for the development and improvement of PA policies and programmes in cities. **Output:** Messaging and programming defined for the promotion of CITY-MOVE MDCA tool.

8. Outputs and DEC Indicators

Table 5. Activities' Outputs and Specific Indicators based on section 6. DEC Tools and Channels.

Objectives	Specific Objectives	Activities	Outputs	Indicators
1. Effectively showcase and amplify the activities and outcomes of the project at the international, regional, and local levels.	1.1. International Level.	1.1.1. Project Branding.	Branding Manual.	1 Branding manual
		1.1.2. Website development	Project's Website	1 Project's Website
		1.1.3. Social media	Social media handles	6000 shares
		1.1.4. Social Media Campaigns.	Yearly DEC programming.	4 DEC Programming.
		1.1.5. Articles, blogs, and podcasts.	5 news articles/5 Podcasts	5 news articles/city; 500 podcast listeners; 1,000 followers/channel
		1.1.6. Partner Newsletters and Events.	Project published in 1-2 global partner newsletters/events/year	5 invitations to global events 5000 conference attendees
		1.1.7 Project Meetings.	Initial and final reciprocal learning meetings	2 meetings; 50 participants/meeting
		1.1.8 Online project meetings.	Monthly meetings with 18 participants per meeting.	48 meetings; 18 participants/meeting
	1.2. Regional Level.	1.2.1. CoP platform for regional exchange.	Messaging and programming defined.	3 CoP meetings: 20 participants/CoP meeting; 10 messages/year; 5,000 attendees
		1.2.2. Partner's Newsletters.	Project showcased in 2 regional partner newsletters per year.	Project showcased in 8 regional partner newsletters
1.3. City Level.	1.3.1. Promote the City's progress and the Living Labs (LL)	Messaging and programming defined.	2 HCPs/city reached in LL; 50/city receive info; 2 trainings/ city	
	1.3.2. Local Media Network.	Local press/media database created	1 Spreadsheet with press/media contact info	
2. Promote the data and findings from the evaluation of 13	2.1. Enhance Visibility	2.1.1. Getting research into policy & practice (GRIPP).	Policy briefs delivered.	12 policy makers reached; 50 policy makers/cities receive policy briefs.

PA interventions (Annex 2) ensuring that these findings are accessible and understandable to a diverse range of stakeholders.	2.2. Strategic Communication Development.	2.2.1. Present the results of the Living Labs (LL)	LL's progress and results showcased in social media. Messaging and programming defined.	Messaging included in the yearly DEC Programming
		2.2.2. Social Media City Progress	City's progress and results showcased in social media.	Messaging included in the yearly DEC Programming
		2.2.3. Press releases	5 articles published in targeted media	5 articles targeted media; 1,000 followers/channel; 5 orgs./city reached
		2.2.4. Scientific publications.	4 cross-city articles published in high impact journals; 12 articles presented on city findings in WoS indexed journals and results presented at 5 international conferences.	5,000 paper downloads; 10 citations in global reports; 5 invitations to global events; 5,000 Conference attendees
		2.2.5. CORDIS	13 publications on EU websites; 10 interactions with EU stakeholders.	13 publications on EU websites; 10 interactions with EU stakeholders.
		2.3.1. Skills & training audit.	Training content available on website.	Webpage with training content
		2.3.2. Peer-to-peer support & training of junior researchers.	Capacity building plan	1 Capacity building plan
3. Position CITY-MOVE as a notable contribution in the field of PA while raising awareness, showcasing the results of the project, and promoting the replication of the City-GAPPA interventions.	3.1. Global Dissemination and Collaboration	3.1.1. Knowledge sharing in Ljubljana Conference	Project's results presented in an international conference.	Project's final results presented in Ljubljana Conference
		3.1.2. Share the Knowledge Library	Inclusion of CITY-MOVE publications in the Knowledge Library.	Inclusion of CITY-MOVE publications in the Knowledge Library.
	3.2. Digital access promotion.	3.2.1. Repository Promotion.	Messaging and programming defined.	100 users in 3 continents; 500 visits to repo./ year
	3.3. MCDA tool promotion.	3.3.1. MCDA tool promotion.	Messaging and programming defined.	Messaging included in the yearly DEC Programming

9. Communications Tactics

Project Identity

CITY-Move will have a visual identity that represents physical activity in six cities with diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts. The logo represents physical activity through the M of CITY-MOVE

and the diversity of cities in the project through the different design of the buildings that form the skyline and the variety of colours presented.

Figure 1. CITY-MOVE logo.

To support this work, a set of branding guidelines or style guide was produced W21 and made available for project partners, some samples of the branding manual are found below:

Clean post without additional text

Clean post without additional text with a picture to provide updates of a specific city.

10. Timeline

Table 6. DEC Strategy timeline.

Objectives	Specific Objectives	Activities	2024				2025				2026				2027				
			Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
1. Effectively showcase and amplify the activities and outcomes of the project at the international, regional and local levels.	1.1. International Level.	1.1.1. Project Branding.																	
		1.1.2. Website development																	
		1.1.3. Social Media																	
		1.1.4. Social Media Campaigns.			M3.1				D1.2 M1.3	D1.1 M7.3			M5.2	D3.1				M5.4	
		1.1.5. Articles, blogs and podcasts.																	
		1.1.6. Partner Newsletters and Events.																	
		1.1.7. Project Meetings.			M7.1														
		1.1.8. Online project meetings.																	
	1.2. Regional Level.	1.2.1. CoP platform for regional exchange.								M6.2									
		1.2.2. Partner's Newsletters.																	
1.3. City Level.	1.3.1. Promote the City's progress and the Living Labs (LL)								M2.1									D2.1	
	1.3.2. Local Media Network.																		
2. Promote the data and findings from the evaluation of 13 PA interventions (Annex 2) ensuring that these findings are accessible and understandable to a diverse range of stakeholders.	2.1. Enhance Visibility	2.1.1. Getting research into policy & practice (GRIPP).																M4.1 M4.2	
	2.2. Strategic Communication Development.	2.2.1. Present the results of the Living Labs (LL)								M2.1									M2.2
		2.2.2. Social Media City Progress																	M5.3
		2.2.3. Press releases																	
		2.2.4. Scientific publications.																	D3.2
		2.2.5. CORDIS																	
	2.3. Peer-to-peer support & training of junior researchers.	2.3.1. Skills & training audit.																	M6.1
		2.3.2. Peer-to-peer support & training of junior researchers.																	
3. Position CITY-MOVE as a notable contribution in the field of PA while raising awareness, showcasing the results of the project, and promoting the replication of the City-GAPPA interventions.	3.1. Global Dissemination and Collaboration	3.1.1. Knowledge sharing in Ljubljana Conference																	
		3.1.2. Share the Knowledge Library																	D6.2
	3.2. Digital access promotion.	3.2.1. Repository Promotion.																	
	3.3. MCDA tool promotion.	3.3.1. MCDA tool promotion.																D5.1 D5.2	

The DEC Strategy timeline and specific yearly programming can be found [here](#).

11. Annexes

Annex 1. CITY-MOVE Network

Table 7. *Networks and international organisations*

CITY-MOVE Partner	Organisation	Abbr.	Description	Website	Reach
Walk21	United Nations	UN	intergovernmental organisation whose stated purposes are to maintain international peace and security, develop friendly relations among nations, achieve international cooperation, and serve as a centre for harmonising the actions of nations. It is the world's largest international organisation.	www.un.org	Global
	UN Environment Programme	UNEP	UNEP is the leading global authority on the environment.	www.unep.org	Global
	UN Human Settlements Programme	UN-Habitat	UN agency that promotes socially and environmentally sustainable towns and cities.	www.unhabitat.org	Global
	Global Observatory of Healthy and Sustainable Cities	GOHSC	Multi-institutional, transdisciplinary, open science initiative providing evidence-based spatial and urban policy indicators to advocate for and track progress towards healthy and sustainable cities for all.	www.healthysustainablecities.org	Global
	International Network for Transport and Access in Low-Income Countries	INTALInC	INTALInC brings together partners from across the globe to find innovative ways to address the mobility needs of vulnerable, urban populations.	https://intalinc.org	Global
Walk21, UA	World Health Organization	WHO	UN agency that connects nations, partners and people to promote health	www.who.int	Global
UA	Healthy Cities Network	HCN	WHO organised global movement working to put health high on the social, economic and political agenda of city governments.	https://www.who.int/europe/groups/who-european-healthy-cities-	Regional, Europe

				network	
	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services	IPBES	Intergovernmental organisation established to improve the interface between science and policy on issues of biodiversity and ecosystem services.	www.ipbes.net	Global
City of Antwerp	EU Mission on 100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities	EU Missions	EU Missions are a new way to bring concrete solutions to some of our greatest challenges. They have ambitious goals and will deliver tangible results by 2030.	EU Missions	Regional, Europe
	ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability	ICLEI	Works at multiple scales, building connections across local, regional, national and global actors and policies.	https://iclei.org/	Global
	NCD Alliance	NCDA	Civil society network includes +67 national and regional alliances and over 300 members in 80 countries dedicated to improving noncommunicable diseases prevention and control worldwide.	https://ncdalliance.org/	Global

Annex 2. Identified City-GAPPA Interventions

Lima

1. **Pan American Games Legacy (early stage).** Pan American and Parapan American Games (Legacy) is an entity which aims to improve access to, and increase use of sports facilities installations, in districts such as Villa María del Triunfo, a district with great inequality (398,433 inhabitants where 18.4% live in poverty). CITY-MOVE target is to reach approximately 5% of those, meaning 20,000 people. It is not yet known how this process can be best targeted to the needs of people.
2. **Green Belt Independencia (late stage).** This initiative has developed an urban park on the fringes of the district of Independencia (about 211,360 inhabitants of which 14.8% live in poverty). The Green Belt avoids urban expansion towards sensitive ecosystems, contributes to disaster risk management and climate adaptation while aiming to improve well-being and health in the district. However, its effects on PA and health indicators have not yet been evaluated.

Bogotá

1. **Happiness Centres (early stage).** 7 Happiness centres (Centros Felicidad) with an area of 12,000 m² each are designed for exercise, recreation, leisure and culture free to the surrounding community, covering approximately 200,000 inhabitants. However, it is unclear if they are enhancing PA among people living in deprived neighbourhoods or if add-on measures are needed to promote PA. CITY-MOVE target is to reach 5% meaning 10,000 people.
2. **Ciclovía (late stage).** This mass participation event, involves closure of 120 km of roads on Sundays for the last 50 years to allow for pedestrians and cyclists to undertake recreational PA. It reaches 0.6-1.4 million participants every week, with 77% having a low income. While Ciclovía has proven successful and cost-effective in Bogota, its success has not been well replicated in other cities. CITY-MOVE will thus aim to identify cross-contextual lessons learnt for effectiveness.

Kampala

1. **Car-Free Day (early stage).** The car-free day started in 2011 –the first in Africa– and was relaunched in the central business district in 2023 (830,000 inhabitants) to encourage PA, reduce carbon emissions and improve air quality. However, it is not known to what extent the car-free day promotes PA or how it can be expanded in geographic scope or regularity.
2. **NMT Pilot Corridor (late stage).** The first non-motorised transport (NMT) strategy in Africa was published in 2012 and invested in upgrading road quality of 8 important roads in the city, codenamed NMT Pilot Corridor. With 42% of the population using walking as their main mode of transport, potential reach is 714,000 people, but the NMT has not led to increased utilisation and safety. A recently committed to a population-based survey to collect data from users and non-users on barriers and experiences, which will feed into the CITY-MOVE interventions.

Antwerp

1. **'Linkeroever' Safe Streets for Girls (early stage).** 'Linkeroever' (122,000 people) reduces street intimidation of girls in the city, aiming to create a safe space for them to be social. There is scope to use sports to entice girls to use urban spaces, but it is not yet known how best to achieve this. Antwerp has 11,000 girls aged 10-19, of which the project ultimately aims to reach at least 50% being 5500.
2. **Health Kiosk (late stage).** The 'Health Kiosk' is a connecting centre between neighbourhood and partners for health prevention located in the deprived neighbourhood Borgerhout reaching 70 people weekly. CITY-MOVE evaluations will focus on sustainability & scale-up.
3. **Square Full of Health (failed project).** The 'Square Full of Health' (Paardenmarkt) was meant to redesign a centre street in co-creation with shop owners, and inhabitants, but despite many participatory sessions, authorities decided not to deliver the interventions. The obstacles have not been evaluated.

Rotterdam

1. **Green Connection (early stage).** A green walking route will be created that connects separate green spaces in Rotterdam-South. This green route will promote and integrate

opportunities for social community building, gardening and physical activity (walking/cycling). The intervention focuses on neighbourhood inhabitants in Rotterdam-South in general and hard-to-reach groups in particular, such as migrant groups. CITY-MOVE focus to be defined.

2. **Green Walking Routes (late stage).** The Green Walking Routes in Middenland and Overschie are already implemented and used by the population. These routes are combined with the green prescription program by General Practitioners and have the support of social support organisations. CITY-MOVE evaluations will focus on sustainability.

Ljubljana

1. **Walking Gaming App (early stage).** A move app for citizens will be developed with a gaming approach. It aims to educate and encourage exercise for those citizens that do not respond nor engage (due to physical or mental limitations) in mass events and is harder to motivate to adopt a healthy lifestyle and PA (12% people live below the risk of poverty threshold in Slovenia, 20% being elderly). CITY-MOVE aims to reach 2,5% of the city population of approx. 7000 people.
2. **Walk Along the Wire Event (late stage).** This event, held each year in May, involves 3000 participants of at least 65 years and includes special trails for children/elderly. Despite mass participation in Walk along the Wire, there have been few evaluations to measure impact of participation on physical and mental health. CITY-MOVE results will be used to increase the impact, reduce the carbon footprint and update the event, which has reached and surpassed its maturity after several decades.

Annex 3. Identified Relevant Scientific Journals

Health Education Journals

The following list of journals is intended as a starting point in your health education research.

- [ACHPER Healthy Lifestyles Journal](#)
- [Adolescent & Family Health](#)
- [Advances in Health Sciences Education](#)
- [American Journal of Health Education](#)
- [Child Care Health and Development](#)
- [Current Health Teens](#)
- [Education for Health](#)
- [Health Education](#)
- [Health Education Research](#)
- [Health, Physical Education, and Recreation, Exercise and Sport Sciences](#)
- [Health & Place](#)
- [Journal of Physical Activity & Health](#)
- [Journal of School Health](#)
- [Ovidius University Annals, Series Physical Education and Sport/Science, Movement and Health](#)
- [Physical & Health Education Journal](#)

- [Quest](#)

Physical education journals

The following list of journals is intended as a starting point in your physical education research.

- [Asia-Pacific Journal of Health, Sport and Physical Education](#)
- [Asian Journal of Exercise and Sports Science](#)
- [Illinois Journal for Health, Physical Education, Recreation & Dance](#)
- [International Journal of Exercise Science](#)
- [International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology](#)
- [Isokinetics and Exercise Science](#)
- [Journal of Applied Physiology: Respiratory, Environmental and Exercise Physiology](#)
- [Journal of Exercise Science and Fitness](#)
- [Journal of Physical Activity & Health](#)
- [Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance](#)
- [Journal of Teaching in Physical Education](#)
- [Journal of the Philosophy of Sport](#)
- [Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science](#)
- [Missouri Journal of Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Dance](#)
- [Ovidius University Annals, Series Physical Education and Sport/Science, Movement and Health](#)
- [Physical & Health Education Journal](#)
- [Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy](#)
- [Psychology of Sport and Exercise](#)
- [Qualitative Research in Sport and Exercise](#)
- [Sport & Exercise Psychology Review](#)
- [The Physical Educator](#)

